

An Inequality for the Intermediate Point in Lagrange's Theorem, Using Quadrature Formulas

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Abstract:

Starting from an inequality presented by professor A. Lupas (1973), which shown that the intermediate point of the logarithmic function in Lagrange's theorem is between the arithmetic mean and the geometric mean of the the limits of the interval on which the function is defined, in this paper we will find a sharp estimation of the intermediate point, using a quadrature formula found by I. Popa in 2005, which was generalized by A.N. Branga in 2010.

Keywords: *Lagrange's theorem, intermediate point, quadrature formula, logarithmic function.*

Introduction

This article is based on an inequality discovered by A. Lupas (1973), regarding the intermediate point of the logarithmic function in Lagrange's theorem.

The purpose of this article is to obtain a refinement of the inequalities presented in Theorem 1. More precisely we will determine $E(a, b)$ and $G(a, b)$ so that

$$\sqrt{ab} < E(a, b) < \ell < G(a, b) < \frac{a+b}{2}.$$

For this goal we will use the following quadrature formula with three nodes, which was presented in the paper of I. Popa (2005).

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \frac{b-a}{6\lambda^2} \left[f\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - \lambda \frac{b-a}{2}\right) + 2(3\lambda^2 - 1)f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f\left(\frac{a+b}{2} + \lambda \frac{b-a}{2}\right) \right] + \frac{3-5\lambda^2}{2} \frac{(b-a)^5}{2880} f^{(4)}(\xi), \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda \in (0, 1]$ and $\xi \in [a, b]$, that has the degree of exactness 3.

We mention that this quadrature formula is a particular case of a more general quadrature obtained by A.N. Branga (2010), choosing the value of the parameter $p = 0$ in Lemma 3 and Theorem 3 of this study.

Materials and Methods

Theorem. 1. The point

$$\ell = \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a} \quad (2)$$

from Lagrange's theorem applied to the function $f(x) = \ln x$ on $[a, b]$, where $a, b > 0$, $b > a$, is located between

$$\sqrt{ab} < \ell < \frac{a+b}{2}. \quad (3)$$

Proof. We consider the function

$$g: (1, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad g(x) = \ln x - \frac{x-1}{\sqrt{x}}.$$

The derivative of the function g is

$$g'(x) = -\frac{(\sqrt{x}-1)^2}{2x\sqrt{x}} < 0,$$

so g is a decreasing function. It follows that

$$g(x) < g(1) = 0,$$

thus

$$\ln x < \frac{x-1}{\sqrt{x}},$$

hence

$$\sqrt{x} < \frac{x-1}{\ln x}. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, defining the function $h: (1, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $h(x) = \ln x - \frac{2x-2}{x+1}$, we find the first-order derivative

$$h'(x) = \frac{(x-1)^2}{x(x+1)^2} > 0,$$

so h is an increasing function. Consequently,

$$h(x) > h(1) = 0,$$

thus

$$\ln x > \frac{2x-2}{x+1},$$

hence

$$\frac{x-1}{\ln x} < \frac{1+x}{2}. \quad (5)$$

Combining the formulas (3) and (4) we get the double inequality

$$\sqrt{x} < \frac{x-1}{\ln x} < \frac{1+x}{2}. \quad (6)$$

Considering $x := \frac{b}{a} > 1$ in relation (5) we obtain

$$\sqrt{\frac{b}{a}} < \frac{\frac{b}{a}-1}{\ln \frac{b}{a}} < \frac{1+\frac{b}{a}}{2},$$

thus

$$\sqrt{ab} < \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a} < \frac{a+b}{2},$$

hence

$$\sqrt{ab} < \ell < \frac{a+b}{2}.$$

Results

The results of this paper will be presented in the form of lemmas and theorems as follows.

Lemma. 2. If $f^{(4)}(x) > 0, \forall x \in [c, d]$, then

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx > \frac{d-c}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3c+d}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{c+3d}{4}\right) \right].$$

Proof. To prove the lemma, formula (6) is used, considering $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$. We obtain

$$\frac{c+d}{2} - \lambda \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{c+d}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{2c+2d-d+c}{4} = \frac{3c+d}{4},$$

$$\frac{c+d}{2} - \lambda \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{c+d}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{2c+2d+d-c}{4} = \frac{c+3d}{4},$$

$$2(3\lambda^2 - 1) = 2\left(3\frac{1}{4} - 1\right) = 2\frac{3-4}{2} = -\frac{1}{2}.$$

Consequently, we find the following three-node quadrature formula:

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx = 2\frac{d-c}{3} \left[f\left(\frac{3c+d}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{2} f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) + f\left(\frac{c+3d}{4}\right) \right] + \frac{7}{8} \frac{(d-c)^5}{2880} f^{(4)}(\xi),$$

i.e.

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx = \frac{d-c}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3c+d}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{c+3d}{4}\right) \right] + \frac{7}{8} \frac{(d-c)^5}{2880} f^{(4)}(\xi),$$

where $\xi \in [c, d]$.

If $f^{(4)} > 0$ on $[c, d]$, it follows that

$$\frac{7}{8} \frac{(d-c)^5}{2880} f^{(4)}(\xi) > 0,$$

so

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx > \frac{d-c}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3c+d}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{c+3d}{4}\right) \right].$$

Applying Lemma 2 for $f(x) = e^x$, $c = \ln a$, $d = \ln b$ we obtain

Theorem 3. For the intermediate point $\ell = \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a}$ of the logarithmic function in Lagrange's theorem we have:

$$\sqrt{ab} < \frac{\sqrt[4]{ab}}{3} [2(\sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b}) - \sqrt[4]{ab}] < \ell. \quad (7)$$

Proof. In order to prove this theorem we will replace in Lemma 2, for $f(x) = e^x$, $c = \ln a$, $d = \ln b$, then we calculate the right and left members of this inequality.

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx = \int_{\ln a}^{\ln b} e^x dx = e^x \Big|_{\ln a}^{\ln b} = e^{\ln b} - e^{\ln a} = b - a,$$

$$\frac{c-d}{3} = \frac{\ln b - \ln a}{3},$$

$$\frac{3c+d}{4} = \frac{3\ln a + \ln b}{4} = \frac{1}{4} \ln(a^3 b) = \ln \sqrt[4]{a^3 b},$$

$$f\left(\frac{3c+d}{4}\right) = e^{\ln \sqrt[4]{a^3b}} = \sqrt[4]{a^3b}.$$

$$\frac{c+d}{2} = \frac{\ln a + \ln b}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \ln(ab) = \ln \sqrt{ab},$$

$$\frac{c+3d}{4} = \frac{\ln a + 3 \ln b}{4} = \frac{1}{4} \ln(ab^3) = \ln \sqrt[4]{ab^3},$$

$$f\left(\frac{c+3d}{4}\right) = e^{\ln \sqrt[4]{ab^3}} = \sqrt[4]{ab^3}.$$

It follows that

$$b - a > \frac{1}{3} (\ln b - \ln a) [2 \sqrt[4]{a^3b} - \sqrt{ab} + 2 \sqrt[4]{ab^3}],$$

hence

$$b - a > \frac{1}{3} (\ln b - \ln a) \sqrt[4]{ab} [2 \sqrt[4]{a^2} - \sqrt[4]{ab} + 2 \sqrt[4]{b^2}],$$

therefore

$$b - a > \frac{1}{3} (\ln b - \ln a) \sqrt[4]{ab} [2 \sqrt{a} - \sqrt[4]{ab} + 2 \sqrt{b}],$$

i.e.

$$\ell = \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a} > \frac{\sqrt[4]{ab}}{3} [2(\sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b}) - \sqrt[4]{ab}].$$

The inequality

$$\sqrt{ab} < \frac{\sqrt[4]{ab}}{3} [2(\sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b}) - \sqrt[4]{ab}]$$

results from

$$\sqrt{xy} < \frac{x+y}{2}, x, y > 0,$$

which implies for $x := \sqrt{a}$, $y := \sqrt{b}$

$$\sqrt{\sqrt{a}\sqrt{b}} < \frac{\sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b}}{2},$$

i.e.

$$2 \sqrt[4]{ab} < \sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b},$$

thus

$$\sqrt{ab} < \frac{\sqrt[4]{ab}}{3} [2(\sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b}) - \sqrt[4]{ab}].$$

Lemma 4. If $f^{(4)} > 0$ on $[c, d]$, $\forall x \in [c, d]$, then

$$\int_c^d f(x) dx > \frac{d-c}{6} [f(c) + 4f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) + f(d)].$$

Proof. Considering in formula (6), $\lambda = 1$, $a = c$, $b = d$ we obtain

$$\frac{c+d}{2} - \lambda \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{c+d}{2} - \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{c+d-d+c}{2} = c,$$

$$\frac{c+d}{2} + \lambda \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{c+d}{2} + \frac{d-c}{2} = \frac{c+d+d-c}{2} = d,$$

$$2(3\lambda^2 - 1) = 2(3 - 1) = 4,$$

Therefore Simpson's formula is deduced

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx = \frac{d-c}{6} [f(c) + 4f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) + f(d)] - \frac{(d-c)^5}{2880} f^{(4)}(\xi) < 0,$$

which implies

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx < \frac{d-c}{6} [f(c) + 4f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) + f(d)].$$

Applying Lemma 4 for $f(x) = e^x$, $c = \ln a$, $d = \ln b$ we get

Theorem 5. For the intermediate point $\ell = \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a}$ of the logarithmic function in Lagrange's theorem we have:

$$\ell < \frac{1}{6} [a + b + 4\sqrt{ab}] < \frac{a+b}{2}.$$

Proof. We substitute $f(x) = e^x$, $c = \ln a$, $d = \ln b$ in Lemma 4 and we calculate:

$$\int_c^d f(x)dx = \int_{\ln a}^{\ln b} e^x dx = e^x \Big|_{\ln a}^{\ln b} = e^{\ln b} - e^{\ln a} = b - a,$$

$$\frac{d-c}{6} = \frac{\ln b - \ln a}{6},$$

$$\frac{c+d}{2} = \frac{\ln a + \ln b}{2},$$

$$f(c) = e^{\ln a} = a,$$

$$f\left(\frac{c+d}{2}\right) = e^{\frac{\ln a + \ln b}{2}} = \sqrt{ab},$$

$$f(d) = e^{\ln b} = b$$

It follows that

$$b - a > \frac{1}{6} (\ln b - \ln a) [a + b + 4\sqrt{ab}],$$

hence

$$\ell = \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a} < \frac{1}{6} [a + b + 4\sqrt{ab}].$$

The inequality

$$\frac{1}{6} [a + b + 4\sqrt{ab}] < \frac{a+b}{2}$$

result from

$$\sqrt{ab} < \frac{a+b}{2},$$

which implies

$$a + b + 4\sqrt{ab} < 3a + 3b,$$

therefore

$$\frac{1}{6} [a + b + 4\sqrt{ab}] < \frac{a+b}{2}.$$

Conclusion

In this paper, we found a refinement of the inequality of A. Lupas (1973), for the intermediate point $\ell = \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a}$ of the logarithmic function in Lagrange's theorem:

$$\sqrt{ab} < \frac{\sqrt[4]{ab}}{3} [2(\sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b}) - \sqrt[4]{ab}] < \ell < \frac{1}{6} [a + b + 4\sqrt{ab}] < \frac{a+b}{2}.$$

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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